

Synthetical Experiments in the Carbazole Series.

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The following work was undertaken with the object of synthesising a molecule composed of three benzene nuclei and two pyrrole nuclei condensed together as represented by formula I. This substance could be used as the starting point for the preparation of many interesting derivatives. Graebe and Ullmann (*Annalen*, 1896, 291, 16) synthesised carbazole by heating 1-phenylbenzotriazole, a reaction which was later used by Ullmann for preparing several derivatives of carbazole, while 3-carboline and 5-carboline have been prepared in a similar way (Lawson, Perkin and Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 6 6; Robinson and Thornley, *ibid*, 1924, 125, 2169). It was thought that it might be possible to construct an indole nucleus upon carbazole in this way from a 1-carbazylbenzotriazole. With the object of preparing 1-carbazylbenzotriazole attempts were made to condense 3-aminocarbazole (II) with *o*-chloronitrobenzene, *o*-bromonitrobenzene, and *m*-nitro-*p*-chlorbenzoic acid, but without success. It was also noticed that 3-bromocarbazole (Ciamician and Silber, *Gazzetta*, 1882, 12, 276) could not be condensed with *o*-nitraniline, *o*-phenylenediamine or even methylamine. Further it was not possible to obtain from it the Grignard compound. It was found, however, that 3-aminocarbazole condensed with 2:4-dinitrochlorbenzene to give 3-(2':4'-dinitroanilino)-carbazole (III), which was converted successively into 3-(2'-amino-4-

nitroanilino)-carbazole, 1:3-carbazyl-5-nitrobenzotriazole and 1:3-carbazyl-5-aminobenzotriazole (IV). Attempts to eliminate nitroge

from the two compounds failed, although Ullmann synthesised 2-aminocarbazole by heating 1-phenyl-5-aminobenzotriazole (V).

A series of experiments was then made with the object of preparing a *phenylene-1:1'-dibenzotriazole*, from which it was hoped that the desired nucleus could be obtained on heating by the loss of two molecules of nitrogen. It was found that 4:6-diamino-1:3-dianilinobenzene (VI) (Nietzki and Schelder, *Ber.*, 1897, **30**, 1668), on treatment with nitrous acid, gave a green, uncrystallisable product, which reacted with aniline to form azophenine. Nevertheless, *p*-dibromobenzene was condensed with *o*-nitraniline and the product was reduced to *p*-di-*o*-aminoanilinobenzene (VII), which gave *p*-phenylene-1:1'-dibenzotriazole (VIII) with nitrous acid. This substance decomposed into resinous products on heating.

The difficulty of adding an indole nucleus to carbazole suggested an investigation of the possibility of building some other heterocyclic structure on the substance. Phenazine compounds have been prepared by oxidising derivatives of 2-aminodiphenylamine (Fischer and Heiler, *Ber.*, 1893, **26**, 383; Fischer, *Ber.*, 1896, **29**, 1873; Nietzki and Simor, *Ber.*, 1895, **28**, 2974), and, with the object of carrying out a similar reaction, 3-(2':4'-dinitroanilino)-carbazole (III) has been reduced to the corresponding *diaminoanilincarbazole*, but this substance, on oxidation, gave products which could not be

purified. With a similar object in view, 1-*p*-2':4'-*diaminoanilino-phenyl-benzotriazole* (IX) was prepared, but attempts to produce both the phenazine and the carbazole systems from this compound again failed. The extreme difficulties in the way of preparing a diamino derivative of carbazole, in which the two amino groups occupy *ortho*-positions to one another, prevented the use of such a compound as the starting point for constructing a new heterocyclic system. 2:7-Diaminocarbazole (Täuber, *Ber.*, 1890, 23, 3256), has been prepared, and some of its derivatives obtained. But it was not possible to isolate a definite compound as a result of nitration.

The ordinary methods for making hydrazines fail in the case of 3-aminocarbazole (Ruff and Stein, *Ber.*, 1901, 34, 1682), so that there is no possibility of carrying out a Fischer indole synthesis with 3-*hydrazinocarbazole*. It was not possible to prepare 3-*methylamino-carbazole* in order that its nitroso derivative could be utilised for indole formation by reducing it in the presence of *cyclohexanone* with subsequent warming in acid solution (see Clemo, and Perkin, jun., *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 1619; Linnell, and Perkin, jun., *ibid.*, p. 2459). When *p*:*p'*-dinitrosodimethylphenylenediamine, (Willstätter, and Pfannenstiel, *Ber.*, 1905, 38, 2249), m. p. 148° was similarly reduced, the nitroso groups were simultaneously eliminated. 9-Aminocarbazole (X) (Wieland, Susser and Fressel, *Annalen*, 1912, 392, 183) has been condensed with *cyclohexanone*, but attempts to remove ammonia from the product to give a substance of the formula (XI) were unsuccessful. It was found, however, that when 9-nitrosohexahydrocarbazole (XII) is reduced in the presence of *cyclohexanone* by means of zinc and acetic acid and the solution subsequently warmed, 8:9-(1':2'-*cyclohexyl*)-*tetrahydrocarbazole* (XIII) is formed.

(X)

(XI)

(XII)

Similarly, 6-*methyl-8:9*-(1':2'-*cyclohexyl*)-*tetrahydrocarbazole* has been obtained from 6-*methylhexahydrocarbazole*. These products behave more like tetrahydrocarbazole than like hexahydrocarbazole,

being insoluble in dilute acids and not giving definite methiodides. By electrolytic reduction 8:9-(1':2'-cyclohexyl)-hexahydrocarbazole (XIV) has been prepared, and this substance is quite basic, dissolving in dilute acids and giving a definite methiodide.

(XIII)

(XIV)

(XV)

Borsche, Witte, and Bothe (*Annalen*, 1908, 369, 73) oxidised tetrahydrocarbazole to carbazole by heating with lead oxide while the same reaction can be carried out by heating with sulphur in quinoline solution (Perkin and Plant, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 128, 694). Attempts to convert the compounds described above into the parent substance represented by formula (XV) by these methods were not successful, although it was found that hexahydrocarbazole could be oxidised to carbazole.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The following method was found to be the most convenient for the preparation of the comparatively large quantities of 3-aminocarbazole required for these investigations (compare D.R.P., 1913/294016 ; Ruff, and Stein, *Ber.*, 1901, 34, 1677 ; Ziersch, *Ber.*, 1909, 42, 3798 ; D.R.P., 1901/184983 ; Schwalbe, and Wolff, *Ber.*, 1911, 44, 285 ; Lindemann, *Ber.*, 1924, 57, 557). Carbazole (50 g.) was dissolved in boiling acetic acid (800 c.c.) and, while slowly cooling the solution, sodium nitrite (21 g.) was gradually added. Without further heating, nitric acid (38 c.c. of *d* 1.4) was added drop by drop with vigorous stirring, and 9-nitroso-3-nitrocarbazole separated. After half an hour the product (60 g., m. p. 164°) was collected, washed with alcohol and suspended in alcohol (600 g.). Molten, crystallised sodium sulphide (500 g.) was then added gradually, and the mixture boiled under reflux for 5 hours, during which 3-aminocarbazole separated. The alcohol was removed by distillation, the residue diluted with water and the product (40 g., m. p. 251°) was

collected and washed with ether. 3-Aminocarbazole crystallised from toluene melts at 258° when pure.

3-(2':4'-Dinitroanilino)-carbazole (III).—3-Aminocarbazole (18 g.) was suspended in alcohol (200 c.c.) containing 2:4-dinitrochlorobenzene (20 g.), and finely powdered sodium acetate (20 g.). The mixture was boiled under reflux for two hours when a red crystalline mass separated. Excess of water was added to the cooled mixture, the precipitate collected and dried. The yield was quantitative and the crude product melted at 255°. A portion of it was recrystallised from nitrobenzene. Thin bright scarlet prisms, m. p. 258°. (Found: N, 16·0. $C_{14}H_{10}O_4N_4$ requires N, 16·1 per cent.).

3-(2'-Amino-4'-nitroanilino)-carbazole.—The dinitro compound (III) (17·4 g.) was suspended in ten times its weight of boiling alcohol. Freshly prepared hot sodium hydrogen sulphide solution (42 g. of crystallised sodium sulphide converted into the hydrosulphide by the addition of the requisite amount of conc. HCl to the fused mass), was gradually added and vigorously stirred. Care must be taken in this operation as the reaction is apt to become violent. The mixture was then boiled under reflux for two hours. On cooling and dilution the aminonitroanilino-compound separated out in quantitative yield. It was filtered and dried at 80°. The product was fairly pure and melted at 242°. A portion of it was recrystallised from xylene. Chocolate brown rectangular prisms, darken between 220° and 250° and melt at 256°-258°. (Found: N, 17·3. $C_{13}H_{10}O_2N_4$ requires N, 17·6 per cent.).

It was also possible to obtain the above compound by directly reducing the dinitro compound (III) after its formation. The compound dissolved in alcoholic hydrochloric acid with a deep red colour and was sparingly soluble in the usual organic solvents.

1:3-Carbasyl-5-nitrobenzotriazole.—A solution of the hydrochloride of the above described nitramine in alcohol was treated with a conc. solution of the requisite quantity of sodium nitrite, with vigorous stirring, at 5°. The insoluble *triazole* gradually separated out as a dark green precipitate. After keeping for 2 hours at 0° the mixture was filtered out and the residue dried. The yield was quantitative. Pale yellow prisms (from xylene) melting with decomposition at 283°. (Found: N, 21·1. $C_{13}H_{11}O_2N_4$ requires N, 21·3 per cent.).

1:3-Carbasyl-5-aminobenzotriazole (IV).—The above nitro body was mixed with a little less than the theoretical quantity of stannous chloride and hydrochloric acid and heated under reflux for one hour.

On cooling, the double compound of the amine with stannic chloride separated out. This was collected, suspended in boiling water and decomposed by hydrogen sulphide. On cooling the precipitate consisting of the amine hydrochloride and stannic sulphide was filtered and extracted with boiling alcohol. The amine was precipitated from the extract by the addition of ammonia. Colourless plates (from xylene), m. p. 187-190°. (Found: C, 72.3; H, 4.6. $C_{15}H_{15}N_5$ requires C, 72.2; H, 4.3 per cent.).

The acetyl derivative of the amine was obtained by dissolving the compound in ethyl acetate and adding a slight excess of acetic anhydride. Rectangular plates, m. p. 292°. (Found: C, 70.4; H, 4.4; N, 20.5. $C_{10}H_{10}ON_5$ requires C, 70.1; H, 4.4; N, 20.5 per cent.).

Among the decomposition products of the compound during attempts at ring formation a small quantity of carbazole could be identified.

The Action of Nitrous Acid on 4:6-Diamino-1:3-dianilinobenzene (VI).—4:6-Dinitro-1:3-dianilinobenzene (Nietzki, and Schelder, *loc. cit.*) was however more easily reduced by treating the compound (35 g.) in alcohol with sodium hydrogen sulphide (from 164 g. of Na_2S , $9H_2O$) and boiling the mixture under reflux for 12 hours. The alcohol was then distilled over. The residue was diluted, the precipitate collected and washed successively with alcohol and benzene until it was obtained in colourless needles, m.p. 207° (yield 50 per cent.).

The diamine was suspended in acetic acid containing the requisite quantity of conc. HCl, and the calculated quantity of amyl nitrite was gradually added with vigorous stirring and cooling. A green mass separated which was collected after two hours. It was found impossible to crystallise it from any solvent. The same substance was formed when nitrous acid was allowed to act upon the diamine under varied conditions. An analysis of the body prepared by using pure substances showed that it contained chlorine.

However on attempting to recrystallise it from aniline a beautiful red compound was obtained which could then be recrystallised from xylene. Shining red plates, m. p. 253°. (Found: C, 82; H, 5.5; N, 12.6. $C_{10}H_{10}N_4$ requires C, 81.8; H, 5.4; N, 12.7 per cent.). It could not be acetylated or benzoylated. Its colour reaction with strong sulphuric acid was identical with that of azophenine and it was identified as such by converting it into flourindine. The green substance gave the corresponding derivative with toluidine. Red plates (from xylene), m. p. 264.5°. (Found:

C, 82.4 ; H, 6.4 ; N, 11.7. $C_{12}H_{11}N_3$ requires C, 82.5 ; H, 6.1 ; N, 11.9 per cent.). It would not condense with either mono-methyl or dimethyl anilines.

p-Di-(*o*-nitranilino)-benzene.—To a mixture of *p*-dibromobenzene (25 g.), *o*-nitraniline (30 g.) and finely powdered anhydrous potassium carbonate (30 g.), nitrobenzene (150 c.c.), a pinch of copper powder was added and the mixture heated at 200°, with efficient stirring for 6 hours when a deep red colour gradually developed. The solution was filtered hot when the condensation product crystallised. It was collected (30 g.) and washed with benzene, m. p. 228°. This crude product was treated with boiling alcohol to remove some 2-nitro-4'-bromodiphenylamine formed at the same time; yellowish red prisms from alcohol, m. p. 162°. (Found: N, 9.6. $C_{12}H_9O_2N_3Br$ requires N, 9.7 per cent.). A small portion of the *diainilino* compound was then recrystallised from nitrobenzene. Bright red prisms, m. p. 233°. (Found: N, 15.8. $C_{12}H_9O_2N_3$ requires N, 16 per cent.).

p-Di-(*o*-aminoanilino)-benzene (VII).—The reduction of the above dinitro compound is best accomplished in alcoholic suspension by means of sodium hydrogen sulphide. After refluxing for 12 hours the *diamine* separated in shining white plates (yield 90%), which, on recrystallisation from xylene as colourless rhombic plates, melted at 159°. (Found: N, 19.1. $C_{10}H_{11}N_3$ requires N, 19.3 per cent.).

p-Phenylene-1:1'-dibenzotriazole (VIII).—The finely powdered diamine (14.5 g.) was suspended in acetic acid (150 c.c.) containing conc. HCl (10 c.c.). The mixture was kept in ice well stirred. Sodium nitrite (7 g.) in conc. solution was gradually added, the temperature being maintained at 10°. After standing for two hours excess of water was added, the precipitate collected, dried and crystallised from nitrobenzene. Rectangular plates, m. p. 279°. (Found: N, 26.9. $C_{13}H_{11}N_5$ requires N, 26.9 per cent.).

It was not possible to identify any pure substance amongst the decomposition products of this compound during attempts at ring formation. Experiments were also tried to form only one triazole ring from the diamine, but without success. The unchanged diamine and the dibenzotriazole could be separated by extraction with xylene owing to the greater solubility of the former.

3-(2':4'-Diaminoanilino)-carbasole.—The compound (III) was reduced by means of the requisite quantity of stannous chloride and hydrochloric acid and the *amine* formed re-crystallised from xylene. Colourless rhombic plates, m. p. 256°. (Found: C, 79.3; H, 5.7; N, 15.2. $C_{13}H_{11}N_3$ requires C, 79.1; H, 5.5; N, 15.4 per cent.).

The analysis indicates that one of the nitro groups has been eliminated during the reduction. A small quantity of it in acetic acid was treated with nitrous acid. A clear solution was obtained which coupled readily with alkaline β -naphthol. Thus it is evident that the product is 3-(4-*aminoanilino*)-*carbazole*.

When however the dinitro body (III, 34 g.) was refluxed in alcohol (350 c.c.) with excess of sodium hydrogen sulphide (from 250 g. of Na_2S , $9\text{H}_2\text{O}$), for 18 hours on a water-bath, the red colour formed at first disappeared entirely and the diamine separated out. This was collected and re-crystallised from xylene (yield 75 per cent.). Colourless rectangular prisms, m. p. 222° . (Found: C, 75.3; H, 5.8; N, 19.1. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_4$, requires C, 75; H, 5.6; N, 19.4 per cent.).

On attempting to oxidise this substance with lead oxide (Fischer and Heiler, *loc. cit.*, and Fischer, *loc. cit.*), or with manganese dioxide in ammonical alcohol (Nietzki and Simon, *loc. cit.*) decomposition products were formed which could not be identified.

1-*p*-2':4'-Dinitroanilinophenylbenzotriazole. — 1-*p*-Aminophenylbenzotriazole (Ullmann, *Annalen*, 1904, 332, 97) was condensed with 2:4-dinitrochlorobenzene by heating the two together in alcohol with sodium acetate under reflux for two hours. A red crystalline product separated. This was collected and recrystallised from xylene; yellowish red prisms, m. p. 228° . (Found: N, 22.3. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_4\text{N}_6$ requires N, 22.3 per cent.).

1-*p*-2':4'-Diaminoanilinophenylbenzotriazole (IX).—The above dinitro compound was reduced by means of stannous chloride and hydrochloric acid. On cooling and passing in HCl gas the stannic chloride double compound of the base separated out. This was collected and decomposed by H_2S . The *diamine* was carefully dried in a desiccator and recrystallised from toluene; colourless prisms, m. p. 155° - 157° . (Found: C, 68.8; H, 5.2; N, 26.4. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_6$ requires C, 68.3; H, 5.1; N, 26.6 per cent.).

2:7-Diaminocarbazole.—The diamine was prepared according to Tauber (*loc. cit.*) and obtained in colourless plates from xylene melting sharply at 260° . The *diacetyl* derivative was obtained in colourless shining plates melting with decomposition at 320° . (Found: C, 68.0; H, 5.3; N, 14.8. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$, requires C, 68.3; H, 5.3; N, 14.9 per cent.). The *dibenzylidene* compound formed pale yellow plates (from xylene), m. p. 290° . (Found: N, 11.4. $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_2$, requires N, 11.3 per cent.). With dimethylaminobenzaldehyde clusters of

yellowish red prisms (from xylene) m. p. 284° were obtained. (Found: N, 15.2. $C_{10}H_{10}N_2$ requires N, 15.2 per cent.)

Several experiments under varied conditions were tried in order to nitrate the diamino compound and its diacetyl derivative. High melting uncrystallisable products were obtained. An attempt was also made to replace the amino groups by hydroxyl groups through the diazo compound, and by treatment with excess of conc. sodium sulphite solution (compare Bucherer, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1904, 69, 49). In the former case an uncrystallisable black solid was formed and in the latter the product was recovered unchanged even after boiling for two days under reflux.

Incidentally it was observed that 3-aminocarbazole was not affected by treatment with sodium sulphite.

Experiments on the Preparation of 3-Methylaminocarbazole.—Since it was found impossible to methylate 3-aminocarbazole directly by means of methyl iodide or dimethyl sulphate even under very vigorous conditions, the benzylidene compound (m. p. 214° , Mazzara and Leonardi, *Gazzetta*, 1891, 21, II, 384) was prepared. But it was not possible to obtain addition compounds of this with methyl iodide or dimethyl sulphate (compare Decker and Becker, *Annalen*, 1912, 395, 362).

3-Aminocarbazole was condensed with *p*-toluenesulphonic chloride by heating the two together in molecular proportions in alcohol containing sodium acetate for 2 hours under reflux. On cooling and dilution, the *sulphonamide* separated out as a crystalline mass. It was then recrystallised from alcohol. Colourless plates, m. p. 227° . (Found: N, 8.3. $C_{11}H_{10}O_2N_2S$ requires N, 8.3 per cent.) It must be mentioned that in the above reaction the substance taken must be quite pure as otherwise a syrupy uncrystallisable solid is formed.

The *sulphonamide* was dissolved in a mixture of acetone and the calculated quantity of caustic soda (25 per cent.) and was methylated by the gradual addition of a slight excess of dimethyl sulphate while keeping the solution throughout alkaline and well stirred. It was allowed to stand for some time and on dilution the *methyl sulphonamide* separated as an oil which soon solidified. Colourless plates (from alcohol), m. p. 168° . (Found. N, 8. $C_{10}H_{10}O_2N_2S$ requires N, 8 per cent.)

Several experiments were made with the object of removing the sulphonyl groups by hydrolysis, but without success. Treatment with acids gave a green uncrystallisable low melting solid.

9-Aminocarbazole (X).—The amine (Wieland, Susser and Fressel,

loc. cit., m. p. 151°, yield 20 per cent.) was dissolved in alcohol to which a slight excess of cyclohexanone had been added and the mixture allowed to stand for 12 hours, after which it was gently refluxed on a water-bath for two hours. On cooling the *hydrasone* separated out in clusters of large well defined rectangular prisms, m. p. 96°. (Found: N, 10·4. $C_{18}H_{18}N_2$ requires N, 10·7 per cent.).

Several experiments were made in order to remove ammonia from the above compound by heating it with various acids to obtain an indole ring. Sticky uncrystallisable solids were formed which could not be purified.

9-Nitrosohexahydrocarbazole (XII).—Hexahydrocarbazole was prepared according to Perkin, jun., and Plant (*J. Chem. Soc.* 1924, 128, 1512) by the electrolytic reduction of tetrahydrocarbazole. It was found that 20 gm. of tetrahydrocarbazole dissolved in 200 c. c. of strong sulphuric acid (d 1·5) were completely reduced by a current of 6 amperes during 16 hours; m. p. 99°.

This was converted to the nitroso derivative by treating its acetic acid solution with sodium nitrite. On diluting the reaction mixture a thick oil separated out which soon solidified to a yellow mass. Large brown prisms from alcohol, m. p. 61-62°. (Found: N, 13·9. $C_{12}H_{14}O N$, requires N, 14·0 per cent. Compare Borsche, Witte and Bothe, *loc. cit.*, p. 70).

An experiment to obtain 9-aminohexahydrocarbazole in the same manner as 9-aminocarbazole resulted in a sticky product consisting mainly of hexahydrocarbazole itself.

8:9-(1:2-cycloHexyl)-tetrahydrocarbazole (XIII).—9-Nitrosohexahydrocarbazole (10 g.) was dissolved in acetic acid (100 c. c.) containing a slight excess of cyclohexanone (7·5 c. c.). Zinc dust (30 g.) was gradually added during 1 hour while vigorous stirring was maintained and the temperature kept as low as possible by ice cooling. The excess of zinc dust was removed and the clear solution allowed to remain overnight. It was then heated on a water-bath for 1 hour, when on cooling and dilution with water a thick gum separated out. This was washed with water and dissolved in ether. The ether solution was repeatedly washed successively with water, dilute hydrochloric acid, and sodium carbonate solution, finally it was shaken up with animal charcoal, filtered and dried. On removing the ether a thick syrupy solid remained which was distilled under reduced pressure. The clear distillate between 230° and 240°/13 mm. solidified on scratching with a drop of methyl alcohol. It was recrystallised from alcohol (yield 8 g.). Colourless prisms, m. p.

88°. (Found: C, 85.9; H, 8.4; N, 5.6. $C_{11}H_{11}N$ requires C, 86.0; H, 8.4; N, 5.6 per cent.).

This compound was insoluble in dilute acids; in dry ether it did not give a *hydrochloride* when hydrochloric acid gas was passed in. The *picrate* was obtained by heating molecular proportions of the substance and picric acid in alcohol for a few minutes. It crystallised out on cooling in bright yellow prisms melting with decomposition at 138°. On heating the substance in a sealed tube with excess of methyl iodide for 12 hours at 100°, and evaporating off the excess of methyl iodide, a compound (colourless prisms) was obtained which was insoluble in ether, contained iodine and melted between 50° and 70° with decomposition. It was not possible to purify it.

Experiments were made to dehydrogenate the above compound. But it was necessary to ascertain first what would happen to hexahydrocarbazole under conditions when tetrahydrocarbazole gave carbazole. It was found that when the vapours of hexahydrocarbazole were passed over heated lead monoxide pure carbazole was formed (Borsche, Witte and Bothe, *loc. cit.*). Sulphur reduction (Perkin, jun., and Plant, *loc. cit.*) also gave carbazole (2 g. from 10 g.).

When however 8:9- (1': 2' -cyclohexyl)- tetrahydrocarbazole was heated with lead monoxide, a tar distilled over. When reduced by sulphur it was not possible to isolate any pure compound.

8:9-(1:2'-cycloHexyl)-tetrahydrocarbazole.—The compound (XIII 5 g.) was dissolved in sulphuric acid (150 c. c., *d* 1.5), and the solution was reduced in the cathode chamber by a current of 6 ampere for 16 hours. On dilution and making alkaline with ammonia a sticky white solid separated out. As this could not be recrystallised from any solvent it was distilled under reduced pressure. The fraction boiling at 235°-245°/15 mm. solidified and was recrystallised from alcohol. Colourless glistening plates, m. p. 144°. (Found: C, 65.8; H, 9.0; N, 5.2. $C_{10}H_{11}N$ requires C, 65.4; H, 9.1; N, 5.5 per cent.).

This compound was markedly basic dissolving in dilute acids. A crystalline *hydrochloride* (m. p. 225° decomp.) was obtained from its ethereal solution. The *picrate* separated from alcohol in yellow prisms melting at 160°. The *methiodide* was prepared by heating it with excess of methyl iodide in a sealed tube at 100° for 12 hours. On cooling it crystallised in colourless prisms melting with decomposition at 187°.

An attempt was made to dehydrogenate this compound by passing its vapour over heated lead monoxide. The product obtained contained some tar. But on recrystallisation from glacial acetic acid a small quantity (0.2 g. from 10 g.) of a crystalline compound (colourless plates) was obtained. This melted at 140° and depressed the melting point of the original compound. But it was not possible to examine it further.

6-Methylhexahydrocarbazole.—6-Methyltetrahydrocarbazole was prepared according to Borsche, Witte and Bothe (*loc. cit.*, p. 62; m. p. 148°).

It was then reduced electrolytically in the same manner a tetrahydrocarbazole. It was noticed that if perfectly pure 6-methyltetrahydrocarbazole was used there was no sign of reduction, but it was not possible to determine the nature of the catalyst. *6-Methylhexahydrocarbazole* separated out as an oil which slowly solidified. As it was not possible to crystallise it owing to its tendency to separate out as an oil, a portion of it was distilled under reduced pressure. The distillate, b. p. 230-240°/14 mm. on solidifying consisted of colourless prisms, m. p. 43-44°. (Found: C, 83.7; H, 9.2; N, 7.4. $C_{13}H_{17}N$ requires C, 83.4; H, 9.1; N, 7.5 per cent.).

The picrate was prepared in the usual manner and was found to melt with decomposition at 174°. The *nitroso derivative* consisted of brownish yellow prisms (from alcohol), m. p. 71°. (Found: N, 13.0. $C_{13}H_{16}ON$, requires N, 13.1 per cent.).

6-Methyl-8:9-(1': 2'-cyclohexyl)-tetrahydrocarbazole - 6-Methyl-9-nitrosohexahydrocarbazole dissolved in acetic acid containing a slight excess of *cyclohexanone* and was reduced by means of zinc dust in the manner described under the preparation of compound (XIII). The product was distilled under reduced pressure. The fraction, b. p. 240°-250°/13 mm., consisted of a thick syrup (2 g. from 10 g. of the nitroso-compound) that did not solidify even after long keeping. An analysis of it showed that nitrogen was 1% too low. The *picrate* was prepared and recrystallised from alcohol, pale yellow prisms decomposing at 118°. (Found: C, 60.8; H, 5.3; N, 11. $C_{20}H_{24}O_2N_2$ requires C, 60.7; H, 5.3; N, 11.3 per cent.).

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